

NICK ADAM’S MENTAL AND PHYSICAL GROWTH IN THE STORIES OF
ERNEST HEMINGWAY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6003741>

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Annotation: *In this article we will discuss the mental and physical growth of Nick Adams in the stories of Ernest Hemingway. We try to analyze the main features of the character of Nick in some stories by E.Hemingway. We mainly focused on the distinctive features and the role of Nick in the plot and composition of the stories.*

Key words: *a story, mental, character, growth, conflict, love, characterize, emotional effect*

The main hero of Ernest Hemingway - Nicholas Adams is a fictional character, the protagonist of two dozen short stories and vignettes written in the 1920s and 1930s. Adams is partly inspired by Hemingway's own experiences, from his summers in Northern Michigan at his family cottage to his service in the Red Cross ambulance corps in World War I. The first of Hemingway's stories to feature Nick Adams were published in his 1925 collection In Our Time, with Adams appearing as a young child in the collection's first story, "Indian Camp". Most of these stories were later collected in a 1972 book, published after Hemingway's death, titled The Nick Adams Stories. They are, for the most part, stories of initiation and adolescence. Taken as a whole, as in The Nick Adams Stories, they chronicle a young man's coming of age in a series of linked episodes. The stories are grouped according to major time periods in Nick's life.

Some critics have read the Nick Adams stories with regard to Hemingway’s narrative technique and point of view. Carl Ficken, commenting on Hemingway’s technique says that it “reveals a definite correlation between Nick’s own state of mind and the degree to which the narrator probes into that mind¹”.

Robert Gibb, who takes Nick to be Hemingway’s extension of himself says that we need not worry about distinguishing between Nick and Hemingway, Whether a story has been written by “Hemingway the writer who wrote in the character of Nick Adams” or by “Nick Adams the writer who, by existing, shaped the idea of a man and his cosmos”, matters not. According to Gibb, “Remembrance goes both ways²”. Hemingway created

¹ Carl Ficken, Point of View in the Nick Adam Stories, ed. J.J.Benson, The Short Stories of Ernest Hemingway: Critical Essays, Duke University Press, p.94.

² Robert Gibb, He Made Him Up: Big Two-Hearted River as Doppelganger, ed. Michael S.Reynolds, Critical essays on Ernest Hemingway’s In Our Time, Boston, G.K. Hall, 1983, pp. 255-256

Nick Adams both out of his life and his strong imaginative powers. From all the above references it becomes perfectly clear that although critics have attributed the Nick Adams stories grown out of Hemingway's childhood memories, his boyhood adventures and his war experiences, Nick is not Hemingway. He was just a fictional person, “a special kind of mask³” for Hemingway. As a writer Hemingway was capable of absolute objectivity and subordination of the self to the needs of his art.

Further development of Nick can be seen in the story “The End of Something” in which he is old enough to take the initiative of breaking his love affair with a girl called Marjorie. Although this story is placed by Philip Young in the postwar stories, it is perhaps better to consider it as another story in Nick's initiation of the pains of love as it tells of the end of a sort of love affair that as an adolescent Nick had with a girl named Marjorie.

Philip Young has placed the fragment after the stories “The Battler” and “The Killers”, where Nick leaves his home and encounters incidents of violence and horror. In both these stories Nick is not shown with any of his family members. In “The Last Good Country” Nick is all the time accompanied by his sister Littless. Although Nick's mother does not make her appearance, she is mentioned by the two as “our mother”. It shows that Nick is still has family ties and hence the fragment should precede the stories where Nick is shown to be on his upon it.

The next story in which Nick still appears as a young boy is “The Doctor and the Doctor's Wife”. In this story on Indian workman tries to pick a fight with Doctor Adams so that he can avoid paying a large bill he owes for treatment of his wife. Nick's opting to go to the woods with his father despite his mother's suggests his love of outdoor life.

Hemingway once said that the story “was about the time when he discovered his father was a coward⁴”.

Conclusion: Thus, after the analysis of the stories we can eventually conclude that Hemingway did not write the Nick Adams stories merely for the sake of creating a particular character. Through Nick's consciousness he wanted us to know more about the condition of the world “in our time” as it best dramatizes for him the issues and questions that are fundamental concerns. These questions related to birth, pain, violence, love and death are essentially existential and an inquiry in to them may still inspire in his struggle to remain free, independent and whole.

³ Philip Young, Ernest Hemingway: A Reconsideration.

⁴ Philip Young, Ernest Hemingway: A Reconsideration, University Park and London, The Pennsylvania State University Press, 1966, p. 33.

THE LIST OF LITERATURE:

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